

SITE GPR	YEAR 10	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.7998 Max: 62.9436	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1204 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 714-716		Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
DEFINITION Reddish tufo layer below 1181				Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU: 1181	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		clay 20% silt 80% sand ___%
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae T <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones ✓ <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
					Compaction	Color
					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) orange
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original			
Southern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
Western Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
Eastern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:			Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1181			Covers: 1205			
Is cut by:			Cuts:			
Is filled by:			Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS Excavated by pickaxe. Large reddish circle near center on surface. Additional reddish patch mid-layer near NE corner.						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: Near center at southern edge of excavation. Shape: Rectangular						
For layers complete this section: Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): level Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) — Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): Thickness increases to the east Nature of the interface with layer below: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North): "Room 1" / SU 1153 			

 = walls

 = reddish spot, perhaps due to the burning of tufo on the surface

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

SU 1204 is an orange layer of soil discovered deep under the cocciopesto floor in Room 1. Due to its orange color and deep red patches, which may represent decaying tufo, it is possible that this area was used to heat tufo blocks in order to prepare the floor surfaces seen elsewhere in Area B. Layer appears to extend under northern wall of Room 1.

<p>SOIL SAMPLING: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%):</p>	<p>NON SOIL SAMPLES: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.): Size:</p>	<p>SIEVING: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%):</p>
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<p>STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor</p>	<p>Filled-out by <u>J. Farr, S. Rous</u> Revised by <u>CHM</u> PDFd by <u>TJM</u> Entered by</p>	<p>on <u>21.07.10</u> on <u>22.07.2010</u> on <u>23.07.2010</u> on</p>
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